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Comparison of Undergraduate Social Studies Instruction Program Elective Course Content and Social Studies Curriculum (2018) Objectives

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Abstract

The 2018 Undergraduate Social Studies Instruction Program included 13 elective field courses. The pre-service teachers should select six elective courses to graduate. The present study aims to compare the content of the above-mentioned elective field courses and the 4th, 5th, 6th and 7th grade social studies curricula (2018) objectives. In the present qualitative study, the data were collected with the document analysis technique. The qualitative study data were analyzed with the Miles & Huberman (1994) reliability formula and the inter-coder agreement was determined as 91.4%. It was determined that 24 objectives in the Turkish Judicial System course, 21 objectives in the Turkish Economy course, 15 objectives in the Globalization and Society course, 10 objectives in the Environmental Education course, 9 objectives in the Historical Evidence in Social Studies Instruction, Local and Oral History, and Information Technologies in Social Studies courses, 8 objectives in the Maps and Applications course, 2 objectives in Current Global Issues, Regional Children's Games in Social Studies Instruction, and Material Design in Social Studies Instruction courses were associated with the social studies curriculum objectives. The objectives specified in Evaluation of In-Classroom Learning, Social Studies Textbook Review, and Drama in Social Studies Instruction courses were not associated with curricular objectives.

Keywords: Social Studies, Elective Field Courses, Curriculum

1. Introduction

The social studies course, described as a primary education course developed based on mass education approach to help the individual realize social self-existence, that includes social sciences such as history, geography, economics, sociology, anthropology, psychology, philosophy, political science, law, and citizenship topics, aims to unify the related learning areas in units or themes, and examines the past, present and future interactions between humans and social and physical environment (MEB, 2005), is a pedagogical course based on social sciences, although the name of the course has been changed several times in the Republic of Turkey history.

The quality of education mainly depends on the quality of teachers. Course aims are only achieved by teachers equipped with the instructed knowledge and skills in a course. Teacher is an individual who graduated from the educational institutions as required by the state and provide general culture, special field and pedagogical formation training, and fulfills the associated duties in accordance with the aims of Turkish National Education (METK, 1973).

In Turkey, teacher training duty was transferred to colleges in 1982, and the most recent curricular regulation that aimed to improve teacher training was enacted in 2018. Previously, the curricula were revised in 1997, 2006 and 2009. Due to the current developments in educational sciences and teacher training, and the structural changes in the Turkish educational system, social needs and demands, restructuring the faculties of education/educational sciences and revision of the teacher training undergraduate programs became a necessity. The new undergraduate teacher training programs were developed and published by YÖK (URL-2).

The revised 2018 Undergraduate Social Studies Teaching Program included 44 hours of theoretical and 12 hours of practical vocational knowledge courses, 26 hours of theoretical and 2 hours of practical general culture courses, and 70 hours of teaching practice courses. Pre-service social studies teachers take 28 compulsory and 6 elective courses out of a total of 34 courses in 8 semesters. The elective course pool was determined in the YÖK Undergraduate Social Studies Teaching Program as follows (URL-1):

Social Studies Instruction Elective Field Course Pool and Course Content

Environmental Education: Basic ecological concepts and principles, ecosystems, food chains, food network, habitat, competition, symbiosis and mutual living, energy flow, circulation of matter, population growth, ecological impact, erosion, soil and water resources, environmental awareness, global studies, institutions and organizations on environmental awareness, environmental education in secondary education curricula.

Current Global Issues: Global political, economic, ecological and social issues, investigation of problems such as hunger, poverty, human rights, population, racism, terrorism, landslide, erosion, earthquake, flood, drought, avalanche, traffic, noise pollution, water pollution, soil pollution, urbanization, drug addiction, energy problem and solutions, alternative approaches, environmental education, the significance of social studies course in these topics, sustainable society discussion and education.

Maps and Mapping Applications: Maps, mapping techniques, map types and implementations, concepts associated with map use and maps in social studies instruction, mapping applications for the instruction of spatial perception skills, mapping and effective mapping applications.

Globalization and Society: Globalization and its effects on Turkey, global developments in the last century, environmental changes, military and economic alliances, effects of globalization on developing nations, Turkey's status in globalization, concepts such as pluralism and multiculturalism (and their significance in social studies instruction) and multicultural education practices.

Evaluation of In-Classroom Learning: Measurement tools employed in education and their features, conventional tools; written exams, quizzes, true-false type tests, multiple choice tests, matching tests, oral exams, multidimensional tools to learn about the students; observation, interviews, performance evaluation, student product files, research papers, research projects, peer assessment, self-assessment, attitude scales, student achievement measurement approaches; learning objective assessment and grading.

Social Studies Textbook Review: Physical, educational design, visual design and lingual expression standards in the textbooks, the adequacy of the textbook content for the program, review of certain existing textbooks based on of content, language, suitability for student level, format, attractiveness, contribution to meaningful learning, ease of instruction, etc.

Regional Children's Games in Social Studies Instruction: Theoretical knowledge on national and regional games and children's games (regional and other games such as knucklebones, tipcat, etc.), the employment of these games in social studies course, practical examples.

Drama in Social Studies Instruction: Definition and meaning of drama, the concepts of psychodrama, creative drama, socio-drama, etc., drama-game relationship, history of drama in education, the structure and application stages of drama in education, drama environment and teacher qualifications, evaluation of drama, the development and application of drama, adequate educational examples.

Material Design in Social Studies Instruction: The employment of field-specific instructional technologies, software types and intended use, educational material design and development principles, determination of material requirements, two- and three-dimensional instructional material design, worksheets, slides, development of instructional material such as VCDs, DVDs, MP3 and MP4 files, in-classroom use of various instructional materials.

Historical Evidence, Local and Oral History in Social Studies Instruction: Theoretical knowledge on historical evidence, local and oral history, research and practice, theoretical and practical examples of historical studies in social studies instruction.

Information Technologies in Social Studies: The employment of computers, mobile phones, other mobile devices, smart boards and the internet in social studies instruction, instructional activities based on information technologies, the employment of social media tools for curricular achievements, applications that aim to improve the competence of pre-service teachers in educational software.

Turkish Judicial System: Basic legal concepts, the origins of modern jurisdiction, historical legal developments in Turkic societies, and contemporary law in Turkey, instruction of required pre-service teacher skills for citizenship, rights and responsibilities instruction and related applications (court judgement analysis, case studies, local and national petitions, etc.).

Turkish Economy: Basic economic concepts, Turkish macroeconomy, related learning areas in social studies (especially production, consumption and distribution learning areas) and instruction of related knowledge, skills, and applications.

Literature review revealed that several studies have been conducted on social studies curricula. These studies were on oral history (Dere, 2018), gender (Başaran, 2019), citizenship (Aydemir, 2018; Şen, 2019; Şiraz & Bay, 2020), social studies instruction approaches (Yalçın & Akhan, 2019), social identity (Karasu Avcı & İbret, 2018), skills (Çoban & Akşit, 2018; Demir & Özyurt, 2021), geographical concepts (Kaçar & Bulut, 2020), multiculturalism (Taş, 2019), women (Tatan, Demir & Oğuz Haçat, 2020). Furthermore, certain studies focused on the analysis of social studies teacher training programs (Akarsu, et al., 2020; Çoban, 2010; Ercan, 2009; Kaymakçı, 2012; Sağdıç, 2018; Tonga, 2012). Kınacı (2021) compared the social studies teacher training programs and curricula that were effective in different periods, and analyzed the course- objective relationship based on various content categories (History, Geography, etc.).

In contrast with previous studies, the current study aimed to focus on singular elective course content in the 2018 social studies teacher training program and determine the number of acquisitions associated with the curriculum in each course content.

The present study aimed to investigate the elective field courses in the undergraduate social studies instruction program and to match the objectives specified in each course with those mentioned in the social studies curriculum. Thus, the following research questions were determined:

Do the environmental education, current global issues, maps and mapping applications, globalization and society, evaluation of in-classroom learning, social studies textbook review, regional children's games in social studies instruction, drama in social studies instruction, material design in social studies instruction, historical

evidence local and oral history in social studies instruction, information technologies in social studies, Turkish judicial system, and Turkish economy course content are associated with the 2018 social studies curriculum objectives? If so, what is the distribution of the number of objectives in the relevant course content based on grade level?

2. Method

2.1. The Research Design

The present study was designed with the qualitative research method. Qualitative research design tackles the richness, texture, and state and feelings associated with raw data, and aims at the comprehension of the collected data collected with an inductive approach (Neuman, 2014). Qualitative research has several advantages over quantitative research. It is more open to innovation; and thus, providing various opportunities to develop novel study designs. The researchers could be creative in effective language use (Creswell, 2014). In other words, the qualitative paradigm allows the researchers to play a dominant role in data collection and analysis (Merriam, 2013). Qualitative research employs data collection methods such as observation and document review. It entails a holistic investigation of events and facts in a realistic setting. Due to these advantages, it was concluded that the comparison of social studies course curriculum achievements and undergraduate social studies instruction program elective field course content would be possible with in depth analysis of the data. Thus, document analysis, a qualitative data collection technique, was preferred in the study.

2.2. Data Collection

In the study, study data were collected with the document analysis technique, a qualitative data collection method.

2.2.1. Document Analysis

In document analysis, all types of official and private documents could be reviewed. Document analysis could be preferred in studies where data could not be collected with surveys, observations or a measurement instrument (Mayring, 2011). The document analysis technique provides several advantages. These include rich material sources, ready-to-use data, error control, and objectivity when compared to the above-mentioned data collection instruments (Merriam, 2013). Due to the above-mentioned advantages and requirements, the authors preferred the document analysis technique. Based on the aim of the study, the 2018 Social Studies Curriculum and the undergraduate social studies teaching program were analyzed in the study.

2.3. Data Analysis and Interpretation

The study data were analyzed with the descriptive analysis method.

2.3.1. Descriptive Analysis

Description is the foundation of qualitative research, and its primary aim is to help the reader observe what the author sees and hear what the author hears (Wolcott, 1994). In descriptive analysis, the data are presented based on main themes, categories and sub-themes, including direct participant quotes, manuscripts and observation notes (Saldana, 2003). The data should be described with direct quotes from the collected study data (interviews, observations and documents). Furthermore, the data should be presented with a descriptive approach to determine the themes and correlation between the themes. In the present study, the authors initially analyzed the documents independently. Consistency was ensured by the collective reanalysis of the documents by the authors and an independent researcher. The qualitative data was analyzed with the Miles & Huberman (1994) reliability formula and the inter-coder agreement was determined as 91.4%. The study findings are presented in tables.

3. Results

The undergraduate social studies teaching program included 13 elective field courses. These are environmental education, globalization and society, current global issues, maps and mapping applications, drama in social studies instruction, evaluation of in-classroom learning, social studies textbook review, regional children's games in social studies instruction, material design in social studies instruction, historical evidence and local and oral history in social studies instruction, information technologies in social studies, Turkish judicial system, and Turkish economy courses. The content of these courses was compared with the objectives in the social studies curricula for various grade levels. Similar objectives in fourth, fifth, sixth and seventh grade curricula are presented in tables below.

Table 1: Comparison of environmental education course and social studies curriculum objectives by grade level.

Course	4th grade	5th grade	6th grade	7th grade	Total
Environmental education	6 objectives	3 objectives	1 objective	0 objective	10 objectives
Sample	SS.4.3.3. Distinguishes natural and anthropogenic elements in their environment.				
Objectives	SS.5.3.2. Explains the impact of the climate on human activities with Daily-life examples.				

As seen in the table, the environmental education course content and social studies course objectives were compared based on the grade level. It was determined that the course content was associated with 6 fourth grade social studies course objectives, 3 fifth grade objectives, and 1 sixth grade objective. The course content was not associated with any seventh grade objectives. It was observed that environmental education course content was associated with 10 social studies curriculum objectives at different grade levels. Table 1 includes certain associated objectives. The code next to the objectives refers to grade level, learning area and the objectives rank.

Table 2: Comparison of current global issues course and social studies curriculum objectives by grade level.

Course	4th grade	5th grade	6th grade	7th grade	Total
Current global issues	1 objective	0 objectives	0 objective	1 objective	2 objectives
Sample	SS.4.3.6. Prepares for natural disasters.				
Objectives	SS.7.7.4. Develop ideas for solving global problems with their peers.				

As seen in the table, current global problems course content and social studies curriculum objectives were compared based on the grade level. The course content was associated with one objective in the fourth grade curriculum, while it was not associated with any objective in the fifth and sixth grade curricula. It was associated with 1 objective in the seventh grade curriculum. A total of 2 objectives were similar in the social studies curriculum and current global issues course content, and these two objectives are presented in Table 2.

Table 3: Comparison of maps and mapping applications course and social studies curriculum objectives by grade level.

Course	4th grade	5th grade	6th grade	7th grade	Total
Maps and mapping applications	3 objectives	1 objective	4 objectives	0 objective	8 objectives
Sample	SS.5.3.1. Indicates the landforms of the locality and surroundings on a map.				
Objectives	SS.6.3.1. Defines the geographical position of the continents, oceans and Turkey with positioning concepts.				

In the table, mapping applications course content and social studies curriculum objectives were compared by grade level, and it was determined that 8 objectives were similar. The course content was associated with 3 fourth grade objectives, 1 fifth grade objective, and 4 sixth grade objectives. No seventh grade objective was associated with the course content. Two matching objectives are presented in Table 3.

Table 4: Comparison of globalization and society course content and social studies curriculum objectives by grade level.

Course	4th grade	5th grade	6th grade	7th grade	Total
Globalization and society	3 objectives	4 objectives	4 objectives	4 objectives	15 objectives
Sample Objectives	SS.5.7.2. Discusses the effect of communication and transportation technologies on economic relations between countries. SS.7.7.4. Develops ideas and suggestions for the solution of global problems with peers.				

As seen in the table, 15 similar objectives were determined in the globalization and society course with the social studies course content in the comparison of the course content and social studies course curricula for different grades. It was observed that the course content was associated with 3 fourth grade objectives and 4 fifth, sixth and seventh grade objectives. Two matching objectives are presented in Table 4.

Table 5: Comparison of drama in social studies instruction, evaluation of in-classroom learning, and social studies textbook review courses and social studies curriculum objectives by grade level.

Course	Sosyal Studies Course Curricula 4th, 5th, 6th and 7th Grade Objectives (2018)
Drama in social studies instruction	0 objective
Evaluation of in-classroom learning	0 objective
Social studies textbook review	0 objective

The social studies curricula objectives were analyzed based on the courses mentioned in Table 5. The course content did not include any objectives listed in the curricula. Thus, it was determined that these three courses were not associated with the social studies curricula objectives.

Table 6: Comparison of regional children's games in social studies instruction course content and social studies curriculum objectives by grade level.

Course	4th grade	5th grade	6th grade	7th grade	Total
Regional children's games in social studies instruction	2 objectives	0 objective	0 objective	0 objective	2 objectives
Sample Objectives	SS.4.2.3. Compares traditional children's games with current games based on differences and similarities. SS.4.7.3. Compares the cultural elements of various countries with the cultural elements of our country (focusing on visual and written communication tools and cultural elements such as dressing, food, games, family relations).				

The regional children's games in social studies instruction course content and the social studies curricula objectives were compared. Only 2 fourth grade objectives were determined in the course content. Course content was not associated with any objectives in other grade curricula.

Table 7: Comparison of material design social studies instruction course content and social studies curriculum objectives by grade level.

Course	4th grade	5th grade	6th grade	7th grade	Total
Material design social studies instruction	2 objectives	0 objective	0 objective	0 objective	2 objectives
Sample Objectives	SS.4.2.1. Determines family history based on oral, written and visual sources and objects.				

Sample Objectives	SS.4.7.1. Introduces various countries (In-classroom presentation of the important features of the researched country with visual materials is ensured).
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The similar objectives in the material design in social studies instruction course content and the social studies curricula for various grades are presented in Table 7. The course content was associated with only 2 fourth grade objectives. There was no relation between the content and fifth, sixth and seventh grade objectives. These 2 objectives are presented in the table.

Table 8: Comparison of historical evidence, local and oral history in social studies instruction course content and social studies curriculum objectives by grade level.

Course	4th grade	5th grade	6th grade	7th grade	Total
Historical evidence, local and oral history in social studies instruction	3 objectives	2 objectives	3 objectives	1 objective	9 objectives
Sample Objectives	SS.5.2.2. Introduces natural and historical assets, objects and artifacts in the vicinity SS.6.6.6. Recognizes the value of women in social life based on Turkish history and current examples.				

The historical evidence, local and oral history in social studies instruction course content was compared with social studies course objectives in different grades and presented in Table 8. It was determined that the course content included 3 fourth grade objectives, 2 fifth grade objectives, 3 sixth grade objectives and 1 seventh grade objective. Thus, the course content included 9 objectives course objectives. Two sample objectives are presented in Table 8.

Table 9: Comparison of information technologies in social studies instruction course content and social studies curriculum objectives by grade level.

Course	4th grade	5th grade	6th grade	7th grade	Total
Information technologies in social studies instruction	3 objectives	3 objectives	1 objective	2 objectives	9 objectives
Sample Objectives	SS.5.4.2. Questions the accuracy and reliability of the data accessed in virtual media. SS.5.4.3. Complies with security rules on virtual media.				

The social studies course curricula objectives for different grades included in the information technologies in social studies instruction course content are presented in Table 9. It was observed that the course content included 3 fourth and fifth grade objectives, 1 sixth grade objective, and 2 seventh grade objectives. Thus, 9 objectives were included in the course content. Two objective examples are presented in Table 9.

Table 10: Comparison of Turkish judicial system course content and social studies curriculum objectives by grade level.

Course	4th grade	5th grade	6th grade	7th grade	Total
Turkish judicial system	4 objectives	8 objectives	7 objectives	5 objectives	24 objectives
Sample Objectives	SS.6.5.4. Defends the necessity and significance of taxation in national economy as a citizenship responsibility. SS.7.6.4. Analyzes the problems encountered in the implementation of democracy.				

The social studies course curricula objectives for different grades included in the Turkish judicial system course content are presented in Table 10. It was determined that the course content included 4 fourth grade objectives, 8

fifth grade objectives, 7 sixth grade objectives, and 5 seventh grade objectives. The course content was associated with 24 objectives. The Turkish judicial system course was the most associated course with the curricula objectives. Two objective examples are presented in Table 10.

Table 11: Comparison of Turkish economy course content and social studies curriculum objectives by grade level.

Course	4th grade	5th grade	6th grade	7th grade	Total
Turkish economy	2 objectives	7 objectives	8 objectives	4 objectives	21 objectives
Sample Objectives	SS.6.5.1. Associates natural resources and economic activities. SS.7.5.2. Analyzes the effects of developments in production technology on social and economic life.				

The social studies course curricula objectives for different grades included in the Turkish economy course content are presented in Table 11. The course content included 2 fourth grade objectives, 7 fifth grade objectives, 8 sixth grade objectives and 4 seventh grade objectives. Thus, the course content was associated 21 social studies curriculum objectives. Furthermore, it was determined that the second grade course included the most number of objectives. Two of these objectives are presented in Table 11.

Table 12: The learning area and related objectives in elective field courses.

Learning area	Objectives	Course and objectives
Individual and society	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information Technologies in SSI (1) Historical Evidence, Local and Oral History in SSI (5)
Culture and heritage	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maps and mapping applications (1) Material Design in SSI (1) Historical Evidence, Local and Oral History in SSI (5) Regional Children's Games in SSI (1)
People, places, and environments	18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental Education (8) Current Global Issues (1) Maps and mapping applications (7) Information Technologies in SSI (1) Turkish Economy (1)
Science, technology, and society	11	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental Education (1) Historical Evidence, Local and Oral History in SSI (1) Turkish Judicial System (3) Information Technologies in SSI (6)
Production, distribution and consumption	18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental Education (1) Information Technologies in SSI (1) Turkish Judicial System (3) Turkish Economy (13)

Active citizenship	13	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Historical Evidence, Local and Oral History in SSI ● (1) Turkish Judicial System (12)
Global connections	24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Current Global Issues (1) ● Regional Children's Games in SSI (1) ● Material Design in SSI (1) ● Globalization and Society (15) Turkish Economy (6)

The objectives included in elective course content and associated learning areas in the social studies curricula are presented in Table 12. It was observed that the individual and society learning area was mostly represented in the Turkish judicial system course objectives. Also, information technologies in social studies and historical evidence, local and oral history in social studies instruction course objectives were associated.

The culture and heritage learning area was mostly associated with the historical evidence, local and oral history in social studies course. Furthermore, the learning area was associated with maps and mapping applications, material design in social studies instruction, and regional children's games in social studies instruction courses.

The people, places and environments learning area was associated with 18 objectives. Out of these objectives, 8 was associated with the environmental education course, and 7 were associated with the maps and mapping applications course. The rest were associated with the current global issues, information technologies and Turkish economy courses.

The science, technology and society learning area was associated with 11 objectives. The information technologies in social studies course included 6 objectives, followed by the Turkish judicial system course with 3 objectives. Also, environmental education and historical evidence, local and oral history in social studies instruction courses were associated with the remaining objectives.

The production, distribution and consumption learning area was associated with 18 objectives. It was determined that the most of these objectives were included in the Turkish economy course content, followed by the Turkish judicial system (3 learning objectives), information technologies in social studies and environmental education courses.

Thirteen objectives were associated with the active citizenship learning area. Twelve were included in Turkish judicial system course, and one was included in the historical evidence, local and oral history in social studies instruction course.

The global connections learning area in the curriculum was associated with 24 objectives. Fifteen objectives were included in the globalization and society course, following by the Turkish economy course (6 objectives), current global issues, regional children's games in social studies instruction and material design in social studies instruction courses.

4. Conclusion, Discussion and Recommendations

Similar to the teacher training programs in various countries such as Germany, the Netherlands, Singapore, and Romania, elective courses are included in the teacher training programs in Turkey (Baskan, et al., 2006; Bilici & Bedirhanoğlu, 2020; Ergun & Ersoy, 2014; Kuzu, 2009; Yazçayır and Yıldırım, 2021). Certain goals, expectations, global changes, competencies in the relevant field, and curricula could be effective in the determination of the elective course content. Comparison of the course content in teacher training programs and various phenomena (e.g., the curricula) associated with this content could help understand the scope and significance of the content. The same could be applied to the undergraduate social studies instruction program.

In the current study, where the elective course content detailed in the 2018 social studies teacher training program were compared to the 2018 social studies curricula, certain findings were determined. The analysis of the 2018 curricula objective based on the course content revealed that the "Turkish judicial system" course included the most objectives. In other words, the "Turkish judicial system" course was associated with a higher number of objectives when compared to other elective field courses, suggesting that the "Turkish judicial system" course included more than one curricular learning area (individual and society, active citizenship, etc.). Although the "Turkish judicial system" course was associated with higher number of curricular objectives in the study, Bursa and Ersoy (2020) reported that the pre-service social studies teachers considered this course as the most unnecessary elective course. Although the Turkish judicial system course was associated with the highest number of curricular objectives, the fact that the course content was considered as the most unnecessary course by the pre-service social studies teachers could be associated with the similarities between the course content and that of other compulsory courses (e.g., Human Rights and Democracy Education and Citizenship). The "Turkish economy" course was also associated with a higher number of objectives in the 2018 curricula when compared to other elective courses. The "Turkish economy" course was mostly associated with 6th grade objectives, and it was associated with the 4th grade objectives the least. Kınacı (2021) reported that the 5th, 6th and 7th grade objectives were the least associated with history and geography disciplines. Considering the content of the above-mentioned elective courses, it could be suggested that these courses could be included in other social science disciplines (economics and law), and the above-mentioned study findings were consistent.

A significant finding in the study was the low number of curricular objectives that were associated with certain elective field courses. These elective courses were the current global issues, regional children's games in social studies instruction, and material design in social studies instruction. It has been determined that these elective courses were directly associated with 2 objectives in 2018 curricula for various grades. The current global issues course included one 4th grade and 7th grade objective, the regional children's games in social studies instruction and material design in social studies instruction courses included 2 4th grade objectives.

It was also determined in the study that certain elective field course content was not associated with any curricular objective. One of these courses was the "evaluation of in-classroom learning". The revision of the teacher training program by Council of Higher Education included the reasons for the revision, the innovations, and the principles of practice introduced in the Regulations for Field Education Courses sub-section. It was stated that the elective course "evaluation of in-classroom learning" was introduced by the curriculum within the context of the practice examples that were included in all curricula to provide a standard for the in-class evaluations and the adequate employment of student assessments in the transition to a higher education level in the future (URL-1). The fact that this course was included in all curricula could have paved the way for the disassociation of course with the social studies curriculum objectives. Similarly, the information on the "Social Studies Textbook Review" course stated that the course was introduced to all curricula and the name of the course will be substituted by the name of the relevant discipline to allow the pre-service teachers to choose quality textbooks (URL-1), demonstrating that this course aimed at the professional development of pre-service teachers. Thus, the "Social Studies Textbook Review" course was not directly associated with any social studies curriculum objective. The final course, which was not directly associated with any social studies curriculum objective, was the Drama in Social Studies Instruction. The analysis of the course content revealed that the course also prioritized the professional development of pre-service teachers, and thus, it was not directly associated with any objective.

The analysis of the elective field courses in the 2018 Social Studies Teacher Training Program demonstrated that the highest number of objectives were observed in the 4th grade curriculum, followed by the 5th and 6th grade curricula with the same number of objectives, and the 7th grade curriculum. In other words, the elective field course content was associated with 29 4th grade objectives, 28 5th and 6th grade objectives, 17 7th grade objectives, and 17 objectives in total in the 2018 Social Studies Teacher Training Program. Thus, it could be suggested that the associations between course content and the curricula were consistent across the 4th, 5th and 6th grades, but lower in the 7th grade.

5. Recommendations

In the study, it was determined that certain course content was only associated with the 4th grade objectives. The learning objectives could be improved to include the objectives specified in other grade curricula. Furthermore, during the revision of teacher training programs, the curriculum content should be based on the grade of the courses that would also be instructed by the pre-service teachers. Social studies courses are instructed in the 5th, 6th and 7th grades. Thus, the relevant content for the associated grade (e.g. objectives, values, skills) should be taken into account in the content development for teacher training programs.

It was determined that certain elective field courses in the Social Studies Teacher Training Program were especially aimed the professional development of pre-service teachers, therefore, certain course content was not directly associated with the curricular objectives. Thus, certain courses such as "Drama in Social Studies Instruction", "Evaluation of In-Classroom Learning" and "Social Studies Textbook Review" that focus on professional development should be instructed in senior classes, especially after certain basic courses (i.e., Social Studies Curricula). Then, the knowledge and skills acquired in the course could be integrated into the field more effectively.

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